

CURRENT ISSUES OF THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TEACHING OF WORLD ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL GEOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

This article provides recommendations on improving the quality of education, its main directions, criteria and indicators, as well as the study of the state of practice, the formation of skills and skills of students in science, the application of innovative technologies on the basis of issues of development of economic and social geography, strengthening the tasks, capabilities of future geography teachers in teaching methodology,

Keywords: economic and social geography, professional training, concept, innovative technology, indicators, Geographic Education, models

АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ МИРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ И СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ГЕОГРАФИИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье даны рекомендации по вопросам развития науки экономической и социальной географии, методики преподавания, повышения качества образования на основе задач, возможностей, усиления внимания будущих учителей географии к развитию науки, изучения ее основных направлений, критериев и показателей и состояния на практике, формирования у студентов навыков и умений по предмету, применения инновационных технологий.

Ключевые слова: экономическая и социальная география, профессиональная подготовка, концепция, инновационные технологии, индикаторы, географическое образование, модели

Currently, the urgent scientific and methodological tasks of updating the content of pedagogical education in the direction of geography, as well as the foundation and development of a system of professional-specialized competencies of future teachers of geography and educational technologies for their formation in students are relevant. These tasks can be solved only on the basis of a single concept of special professional training for future geography teachers, taking into account the traditions and innovations of geographical education in higher and secondary schools.

To do this, it will be advisable to carry out the following works:

- study of the problem of special professional training of future geography teachers in historical and modern aspects, the formation of its new concept, the analysis of the updated content of the geography education of students on its basis;

- theoretical justification of the system of professional and specialized competence of future geography teachers as a result of the integration of cultural and competent approaches to pedagogical education;

- development of logical and semantic models of the development of general pedagogical, objective technologies of special professional training for future geography teachers and the development of local technology for the formation of professional and specialized competencies for students based on contextual educational technology;

- in theory, the application of innovative technologies of future geography teachers and the identification of difficulties in its organization are among the students in the experiment;

- development of a logical-semantic model of innovative technologies in students, analysis of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of this technology in all important modules of special professional training on its basis, development of a complex of pedagogical conditions for economic geography;

- examination of the experimental effectiveness of the application of innovative technologies in the complex of relevant pedagogical conditions carried out by teachers in the process of granting geographical knowledge of World Economic Geography.

The innovation was accepted by the pedagogic wakelikning element Atatida Tasiladi, he proposed ethylganidek, Hali bu shodda uchramagan. The innovation is yangilikning tashuvchisi, einish, practicing olb chiksh varasi (yangi loyihalar, direktivlar, uluv kulanmalari, uluv yurtlaring turlari and bashkalar.) [3]. The current Ildiz otib, yangilikni (or Yangiliklar duplamini) Olib Boradigan Yangilik practices management, uzgartiradi, yangilaidi, Union Yanada samarali kiladi. Innovative

pedagogical practitioner yangiliklarni crack. Shundai kilib, novation zharaen training practitioners to improve karatilgan.

modern teacher dolzarb yohtezhi Yangi, Yanada samaral pedagogical pedagogical technologicalarni izlashdir. Currently, an innovation has been implemented that requires intellectual, ethical and ethical development, provided high-quality education. Biz yashaetgan Jamiat UzLiDeP, a conformist. And Ular Bilan is a geographer of tarlari education. Kelaetgan HH centennial geography requires a guided tour with information about the "continuation" of the EMAS, as well as the work of an independent materials geographer, requiring assistance in conducting analysis. Once again, the students are able to form officials. The personality of the character developing modernity training United important tasks. The post-industrial jamiyatda of yashashi and ishlashi kerak bulgan is a contemporary of the bitiruvchizi school, a famous man asafatlarga gerak:

- working meeting of the President of the Republic of Tajikistan Emomali Rahmon with Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Tajikistan Emomali Rahmon, Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Tajikistan Emomali Rahmon, Chairman of the executive body of state power of the Sughd region Abdurakhmon Kodiri with Chairman of the Majlisi Namoyandagon Majlisi Oli of the Republic of Tajikistan.;

- independent criticism, found old riddles of oling, keraklie ekimney malakali and wise tanlang;

- Izhodiy Hunlay Olish and Tabdan Yangi Yaratish;

- information by Bilan Malakali ishlash;

- heartbreaking olish, jamoada Ishlai olish [5].

Thus, the main strategic direction of the development of the school education system lies in the path of solving the problem of personality-oriented education-the personality of such an education student becomes the focus of the teacher, in which cognitive activity, and not teaching, becomes the leader. In the context of personality-oriented education, the teacher will have a different role and function in the educational process, no less than the traditional system of Education. Now the teacher works not only as a carrier of knowledge and a controlling body, but also as an organizer of the student's independent cognitive activity. In such conditions, the teacher should know the methods and forms of building the educational process that stimulate the independent cognitive activity of the student. This explains the relevance of this study. The need to systematize innovative pedagogical models and technologies, determine their role in the development of the child's personality, show the possibilities and

methods of using innovative technologies and educational models in the process of teaching geography.

As a conclusion, the following can be noted:

- the concept of special professional training for geography teachers is fundamental, in which students combine cultural and qualified approaches in a context of contextual teaching;

- developed a system for the application of innovative technologies in the teaching of World Economic and social geography;

- logical-semantic models of the development of technologies for the formation of professional-specialized competencies among students, demonstrating the essence of the developed innovative approach and the algorithm for its implementation, have been developed.

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